

Hourly Efficiency of Solar Water Collector

Solar Water Heating

Multi-Apartment Residential Buildings in Tel Aviv

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Version 1, 17 September 2021

Abstract

This work demonstrates calculations of solar collector hourly efficiency based on the efficiency curve unique for each collector type.

Collector efficiency depends on solar radiation, collector temperature and ambient temperature.

Three iterations of calculations were applied, showing relatively small differences between the iterations. The calculated yearly efficiency is almost equal to the efficiency determined according to the national standard. Monthly efficiency is in the range of -5.2% to +3.4% difference from the efficiency determined according to the national standard. Higher efficiency is in winter. The maximum hourly efficiency is at 8 o'clock in July, 75.2%.

1. Glossary

E	energy [kcal] (not kcal/hr)
kcal	kilo-calorie, energy unit
Q	energy in time [kcal/hr] (not kcal)
SE	Solar Energy

SWH Solar Water Heater, in this work forced circulation domestic solar water heater for residential units

2. Introduction

Solar water heaters must be installed in new buildings in Israel according to the law. Solar water heaters save 5% of the national electricity consumption [1] and are an important component of the Israeli economy and standard of living. The solar law requires solar water heaters for 9 upper floors of the residential buildings.

The usual solution for residential buildings above 4 floors is a forced circulation system with a central collectors array and separate storage tanks for each apartment.

The efficiency of collectors depends on solar radiation (insolation), collectors' temperature and ambient temperature.

This work is for conditions in Israel/Tel Aviv.

3. Energy Units

This work is in Metric Units. Usually metric units apply Joule as energy unit. In this work the energy unit is also kilocalorie, the energy required to heat 1 kg of water (1 liter) by 1°C. 1 kcal is equal to 4,186.8 Joule, and 1 kJ is equal to 0.23885 kcal. The application of kcal in addition to Joule is very convenient for works involving water heating, as the temperature difference immediately indicates the amount of energy in kcal.

Electric energy is expressed in kWh.

1 kWh is 859.85 kcal and 1 kcal is 1.1630 Wh.

Local time is GMT+2 for the whole year, DST is not considered.

4. Solar Water Heater

The solar water heating system selected for this work is Chromagen and consists of the following main parts:

- central array of solar collectors type CR12-B:
the collector connections are 1"
the efficiency curve of the selected solar collector is $\eta=0.75-4.1x$
the efficiency of the solar collector calculated according to the national standard [1] is = 61.8%
tilt angle 45°
- circulation pump
- individual 150 liter vertical storage tanks H=1070mm, Dia=560mm, all connections ¾", with inside 2.5kW instant backup

Location: Tel Aviv / Israel 32.0929° N, 34.8072° E

5. Tilt Angle

The tilt angle for central solar installations in residential buildings in Israel is 45° [1].

6. Solar Radiation

Solar radiation data for tilt angle 45° in Tel Aviv is from [2].

Table 1 - Solar radiation on tilt angle 45° in Tel Aviv, kcal/m²,day

Tilt	0° horizontal	45°	Δ	Δ
Month	kcal/m ² ,d	kcal/m ² ,d	kcal/m ² ,d	
1	2430	3450	+1,020	+42.0%
2	3260	4120	+860	+26.4%
3	4130	4520	+390	+9.4%
4	5190	4890	-300	-5.8%
5	6140	5200	-940	-15.3%
6	6520	5180	-1,340	-20.6%
7	6440	5270	-1,170	-18.2%
8	5990	5460	-530	-8.8%
9	5080	5380	+300	+5.9%
10	3890	4810	+920	+23.7%
11	2850	4060	+1,210	+42.5%
12	2160	3110	+950	+44.0%
Ave	4507	4621	+114	+2.5%

Chart 1 - Solar Radiation on Tilt Angle 45° in Tel Aviv, kcal/m²,day

7. City Water (Cold Water) Temperature

It is assumed that city water temperature in winter (<+20°C) is 3°C above the average ambient air temperature, and in other periods equals to the monthly average air temperature.

Table 2 - Monthly averages of city water temperature in Tel Aviv

Month	Ta, °C	Tcold, °C
1	12.07	15.07
2	12.70	15.70
3	14.16	17.16
4	18.04	20.00
5	20.02	20.02
6	23.35	23.35
7	25.15	25.15
8	25.52	25.52
9	24.63	24.63
10	21.84	21.84
11	16.55	19.55
12	13.09	16.09

Ta ambient air temperature, month's average, °C

Tcold cold water (city water) temperature, month's average, °C

8. Heating Energy Formula

Formula 1 - Heating energy

$$E = m * c * \Delta t$$

This formula is well described in publication [2].

9. Storage Tank Stratification

According to [5] the stratification in the vertical storage tank is 10.89°C per meter of the storage tank height.

The inner height of the storage tank applied in this work is 850 mm, resulting in 9.26°C stratification.

10. Selected Solar Collector

The solar collector selected for this work is Chromagen CR12-B [4].

The size of this collector is 7,005 kcal/d, net opening 2.55 m².

The standard energy output of 1m² of this collector is 2,747 kcal/d, which according to the Israeli law is suitable for 67 liters storage tank.

Table 3 - Selected solar collector

Collector	Q	V	Q/V	Opening
	kcal/d	Liter	kcal/L	m ²
CR12-B	7,005	170	41.2059	2.55
	2,747	67.001	41	1.00
For each apartment	6,150	150	41	2.24

As the collector efficiency calculations are related to solar radiation on 1 m², also the collector size is 1m², and the relevant volume of the storage tank is 67 liters.

11. Solar Collectors Efficiency Formula

The efficiency of the collector is calculated as explained in publication [1].

The hourly efficiency of the collector depends of the collector temperature which depends on the efficiency of the collector. This results in circular calculations requiring at least 2 iterations.

The first iteration applies standard efficiency of the selected collector, 61.8%.

The second iteration will apply the hourly efficiency of the collector as calculated in the first iteration.

Formula 2 - Solar collector efficiency

$$\eta = a \cdot x + b$$

$$x = (T_m - T_a) / SE \quad [^{\circ}\text{C} \cdot \text{m}^2 / \text{W}]$$

$$T_m = T_0 + SE \text{ [kcal/hr,m}^2\text{]} \cdot \eta_0 / V \quad [^{\circ}\text{C}]$$

$$\eta = a \cdot (T_m - T_a) / SE \text{ [W/m}^2\text{]} + b$$

η solar collector efficiency at point x

a, b characteristic of specific collector; for the collector applied in this work:

$$a = -4.1$$

$$b = 0.75$$

T_m collector mean temperature [$^{\circ}\text{C}$]

T_a ambient temperature [$^{\circ}\text{C}$]

SE global solar radiation (insolation) on the collector at tilt angle

SE is expressed in [W/m^2] for η calculations

SE is expressed in [kcal/hr,m^2] for T_m calculations

T_0 collector average temperature in previous hour [$^{\circ}\text{C}$]

η_0 collector efficiency in previous iteration

for the collector applied in this work the first iteration efficiency is 61.8%

$$\eta_0 = 61.8\%$$

V storage tank volume of the solar heater relevant to 1m² of the solar collector

In this work:

$$V = 67 \text{ liter/m}^2$$

The formula for collector average temperature is based on Formula 1.

The collector temperature before the first solar hour is actually below the ambient temperature, considering the radiation from the collector to the sky at night.

However, in this work, it has an insignificant influence on the collector efficiency and will be neglected.

12. First Iteration of the Calculations

In the first iteration of the calculations the solar collector efficiency is constant and equal to the standard efficiency of the applied collector, 61.8%

Table 4 - Collector hourly efficiency in January and in July – 1st iteration

hr	Jan	Jul
5		59%
6		69%
7	61%	75%
8	71%	77%
9	73%	75%
10	72%	73%
11	70%	70%
12	68%	67%
13	65%	64%
14	59%	60%
15	48%	54%
16	26%	42%
17		14%
Ave	61.4%	61.4%
Max	72.8%	76.6%

13. Hourly Efficiency of Solar Collector

Following are results of 3 iterations for January, April and July.

Table 5 - Hourly Efficiency of Solar Collector - January

hr	Iteration			
	1st	2nd	3rd It	Δ 1-3
7	60.52%	60.59%	60.58%	-0.1%
8	71.45%	70.96%	70.98%	+0.7%
9	72.79%	71.96%	72.02%	+1.1%
10	72.19%	70.94%	71.05%	+1.6%
11	70.33%	68.76%	68.94%	+2.0%
12	67.93%	66.11%	66.38%	+2.3%
13	64.84%	62.82%	63.21%	+2.6%
14	59.39%	57.05%	57.64%	+3.0%
15	48.47%	45.79%	46.78%	+3.6%
16	26.31%	23.72%	25.51%	+3.1%
Ave				+2.0%

Table 6 - Hourly Efficiency of Solar Collector - April

hr	Iteration			
	1st	2nd	3rd It	Δ 1-3
6	64.25%	64.12%	64.13%	+0.2%
7	73.33%	72.69%	72.72%	+0.8%
8	73.96%	73.05%	73.11%	+1.2%
9	72.15%	71.05%	71.14%	+1.4%
10	70.15%	68.84%	68.98%	+1.7%
11	67.66%	66.14%	66.35%	+2.0%
12	63.95%	62.17%	62.50%	+2.3%
13	58.55%	56.61%	57.10%	+2.5%
14	40.59%	38.05%	39.11%	+3.8%
15	12.23%	10.48%	12.39%	-1.3%
Ave				+1.5%

Table 7 - Hourly Efficiency of Solar Collector - July

hr	Iteration			$\Delta 1-3$
	1st	2nd	3rd It	
5	58.73%	58.89%	58.88%	-0.3%
6	69.48%	69.12%	69.14%	+0.5%
7	75.11%	74.19%	74.25%	+1.2%
8	76.56%	75.04%	75.17%	+1.9%
9	75.23%	73.36%	73.56%	+2.3%
10	72.62%	71.22%	71.38%	+1.7%
11	69.94%	68.29%	68.51%	+2.1%
12	66.96%	65.08%	65.40%	+2.4%
13	63.80%	61.85%	62.26%	+2.5%
14	59.75%	57.78%	58.32%	+2.4%
15	53.72%	51.82%	52.57%	+2.2%
16	41.90%	40.33%	41.44%	+1.1%
17	14.28%	14.09%	16.00%	-10.7%
Ave				+0.8%

Running the calculations in 3 iterations improved the results by 1.5% in average.

Table 8 - Hourly Efficiency of Solar Collector – 3rd iteration

hr	Jan	Apr	Jul	Ave
5			58.88%	
6		64.13%	69.14%	
7	60.58%	72.72%	74.25%	69.19%
8	70.98%	73.11%	75.17%	73.09%
9	72.02%	71.14%	73.56%	72.24%
10	71.05%	68.98%	71.38%	70.47%
11	68.94%	66.35%	68.51%	67.94%
12	66.38%	62.50%	65.40%	64.76%
13	63.21%	57.10%	62.26%	60.86%
14	57.64%	39.11%	58.32%	
15	46.78%	12.39%	52.57%	
16	25.51%		41.44%	
17			16.00%	

Chart 2 - Hourly Efficiency of Solar Collector

Axis x is hour of the day.

14. Monthly Averages of Collector Efficiency

The average monthly efficiency of a solar collector is not an average of hourly efficiencies, but the ratio of the total energy supplied by the collector to the solar energy.

Formula 3 - Monthly efficiency of solar collector

$$\eta_{\text{month}} = \frac{\sum(\text{SE}_i * \eta_i)}{\sum(\text{SE}_i)}$$

η_{month} solar collector monthly efficiency

i hour from 1 to 24

SE_i solar energy in hour i

η_i collector efficiency in hour i

Table 9 - Monthly efficiency of solar collector

month	η month	Δ to Ave	Δ to Std	Max
1	61.8%	+2.9%	+0.1%	72.0%
2	60.5%	+0.7%	-2.0%	73.9%
3	60.6%	+0.9%	-1.8%	75.0%
4	59.2%	-1.5%	-4.2%	73.1%
5	58.8%	-2.2%	-4.8%	73.9%
6	58.6%	-2.6%	-5.2%	74.0%
7	59.6%	-0.9%	-3.6%	75.2%
8	59.3%	-1.4%	-4.0%	74.8%
9	59.7%	-0.6%	-3.3%	74.2%
10	59.7%	-0.6%	-3.3%	73.1%
11	62.0%	+3.1%	+0.3%	72.0%
12	63.8%	+6.2%	+3.4%	74.7%
Min	58.6%		-5.2%	
Max	63.8%		+3.4%	

Δ to Ave = difference to the yearly efficiency of the solar collector (60.1%).

Δ to Std = difference to the standard efficiency of the solar collector (61.8%).

Chart 3 - Monthly efficiency of solar collector

15. Solar Collector Yearly Efficiency

Formula 4 - Solar collector yearly efficiency

$$\eta_{\text{year}} = \frac{\sum(\text{SE}_i * \text{D}_i * \eta_i)}{\sum(\text{SE}_i * \text{D}_i)}$$

η_{year} solar collector yearly efficiency

i month from 1 to 12

SE_i daily Solar Energy in month i

D_i number of days in month i

η_i collector efficiency in month i

Table 10 - Yearly efficiency of solar collector

Iteration	η year	Δ to 3rd
Standard	61.77%	+2.8%
1st	61.26%	+1.9%
2nd	59.70%	-0.7%
3rd	60.10%	

The standard efficiency of the solar collector is determined 2.8% above the calculations results. This does not necessary mean that the standard efficiency should be corrected, as this work is related to Tel Aviv with relatively lower solar radiation than in other locations in Israel like Jerusalem, Galilee and Negev.

16. Reference

1. Solar Israel – A practical and legislative model – Joseph Nowarski, Renewable Energy World, March-April 2000, p93-99
2. Energy Balance of Solar Water Heaters – Joseph Nowarski, academia.edu/34457200
3. Heat Transfer in Solar Water Heaters Pipes – Joseph Nowarski, academia.edu/ 34459205
4. Chromagen Solar Thermal Systems
chromagen.co.il, chromagen.com
5. Experimental Measurements of Hot Water Stratification in a Heat Storage Tank
iopscience.iop.org/article/10.1088/1757-899X/471/2/022014

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